

Research Data Management Strategy and Policy at the Institute for Combustion Technology

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Version: 1.0.0
November 28, 2025

Abstract

This institute-wide Research Data Management (RDM) policy establishes binding baseline standards for the responsible handling of research data across all projects at the Institute for Combustion Technology. It provides staff with clarity and guidance throughout the data lifecycle and supports compliance with the FAIR principles. Where external or project-specific requirements specify different or stricter measures, those requirements take precedence.

1 Motivation

The availability of published and unpublished data is essential for reproducing scientific results and opens up important opportunities for further research. Despite the crucial role that data availability plays in scientific work, it is not always ensured, even when data are used in peer-reviewed publications. Requesting data from 516 studies published between two and 22 years earlier, Vines et al. [18] found that only one in five datasets could be retrieved. Several other studies found that authors are often unable or unwilling to share their data [14, 21, 16, 19]. Long-term availability is a particular challenge here, as the availability of published research data can decline rapidly over time after publication [18].

In addition to the mere availability of research data, numerous other requirements must also be met. Wilkinson et al. [22] proposed guiding principles aiming to improve the infrastructure supporting the reuse of scholarly data. According

to these principles, research data should be Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable (FAIR) [22].

The present policy aims to consolidate and implement the requirements of the German Research Foundation (DFG) [2, 3], RWTH Aachen University [15], and ITV's internal objectives while considering the FAIR principles [22]. The policy is structured around a core guideline and three additional guidelines addressing research data management planning, software development, and storage and documentation.

The centralized planning, administration, documentation, storage, and archiving of research data ensures long-term usability. The standardized yet flexible approach facilitates successful research data management while enabling evolving best practices. Group leaders and data stewards working across projects enforce and coordinate the implementation and further development of the strategy. The following sections discuss the last three individual guidelines and the most important goals pursued by using them. Examples of important RDM-related events are illustrated as a timeline in Figure 1. Table 1 summarizes the roles and their current representatives within the ITV data management policy.

Core Guideline

Research data management (RDM) concerns everyone at ITV. All personnel are expected to familiarize themselves with this policy and to implement the procedures explained according to their role. We encourage active participation in the periodic review and enhancement of this policy to ensure its relevance and effectiveness.

Guideline 1

A data management plan maintained in the Research Data Management Organizer (RDMO) is required for each project.

Guideline 2

Software developed at ITV and other text-based data that comply with the license conditions and project-dependent confidentiality requirements must be managed in a git repository in the RWTH GitLab instance.

Guideline 3

All research data, including \LaTeX source code and figures of publications, must be stored or referenced and documented in the Collaborative Scientific Integration Environment (Coscine).

Table 1: Roles and their current representative within the ITV data management strategy.

Role	Current representative
Employee	All scientific staff
Group leaders	Joachim Beeckmann, Hongchao Chu, Fabian Fröde, Michael Gauding, Raymond Langer
Director	Heinz Pitsch

Figure 1: Timeline with examples of RDM events for scientific staff at ITV.

2 Research Data Management Plans

A data management plan (DMP) describes the life cycle of research data from collection to archiving, including all measures to ensure that the data remains available, usable, and understandable. Many funding agencies, especially governmental sources, require a DMP. Therefore, all scientific staff must update their existing DMPs at least every six months and add a DMP for each new project within the first three months. At the ITV, the RDMO tool is used to create DMPs. The group leader and research staff involved in the project are added as owners of a project. For already existing DMPs, the group leader is responsible for adding relevant new employees. The status of each DMP is tracked within the employees' status sheet and discussed during the biannual staff strategy meetings. Choose the ITV catalog and the parent project "ITV general" in RDMO unless you are working in a large-scale project that also requires you to maintain a DMP in RDMO. In that case, the project-specific requirements replace the ITV guidelines and the project-specific catalog can be

used.

3 Software Development and GitLab usage at ITV

Simulations of reactive flows and the evaluation of experiments are part of ITV's daily work and require complex software. Software developed at ITV and other text-based data that meets the license conditions and (project-dependent) confidentiality requirements must be managed in a git repository in the RWTH GitLab instance. The following GitLab groups have been established to keep project data organized and maintain access control. When creating a GitLab repository, please use one of these groups where applicable:

```
RWTH GitLab/  
├── ITV_Code  
├── ITV_Teaching  
└── ITV_Kinetics
```

ITV_Code: Use this group for software development projects that are broadly relevant to ITV research. This includes any kind of code or scripts used in ongoing research activities at the institute.

ITV_Teaching: Reserve this group for data, scripts, or code used solely in courses. Avoid using it for student theses or other individual research projects.

ITV_Kinetics: Place all chemical kinetic models (regardless of detail level) in this group, along with relevant validation databases.

If none of the above groups applies, please use your personal GitLab space.

The FlameMaster repository demonstrates best practices for collaborative development, continuous integration, and version control in ITV's GitLab environment. Depending on the size and complexity of your project, these best practices can be adapted to suit your needs. FlameMaster is a publicly available C++ program package for zero-dimensional combustion and one-dimensional laminar flame calculations, which has been maintained using GitLab since 2015. Currently, the repository includes 86 members associated with the ITV (primarily undergraduate and graduate students below referred to as ITV developers) who use the repository jointly to perform various research tasks, such as the analysis of experimental measurements and the development of detailed chemical kinetic models.

An essential building block for the long-term success of source code development is the implementation of Continuous Integration (CI), i.e., the practice of frequently building and testing a software system during its development. The implementation for FlameMaster relies on the RWTH GitLab instance focusing on the master branch of the repository, where the primary goals are accessibility and interoperability of the source code and reproducibility of simulation results for all FlameMaster developers and users, including numerous exter-

nal researchers and non-academic users. Each commit that an ITV developer pushes to the remote repository hosted in the RWTH GitLab instance triggers a six-stage CI pipeline. Starting from docker images of recent, minimal Linux operating systems, a GitLab runner performs the following steps automatically:

1. Installation of dependencies
2. Configuration and compilation of the software package
3. Execution of unit tests
4. Execution of preprocessing steps for simulations
5. Execution of simulations
6. Public release of the source code on the ITV website.

The success of each step is automatically checked, and a subsequent step is only initiated if the previous one was successful. The ITV developer who pushed the last commit to the repository receives a notification if a step fails. The combined use of CI and GitLab in a large group of developers has several advantages. Executing the CI pipeline after every commit ensures that issues and bugs are detected and fixed promptly. Performing all tests in docker images of recent, minimal Linux operating systems improves the reproducibility of simulation results, a crucial aspect in the field of scientific computing. The automatic release of thoroughly tested software enables external users to access improved software easily, thereby promoting the widespread use of the most recent version of FlameMaster. Moreover, the joint use of an internal git repository by the ITV developers fosters collaboration and long-term improvements of the software, including significant advancements of the source code that the researchers cannot share before peer review in a journal publication.

4 Finding, Storing, and Documenting Research Data in Coscine

Coscine is a central tool for implementing the ITV data management policy. It is ITV’s default application for documenting and storing scientific data, such as journal articles, collected validation datasets, experimental measurement data, simulation inputs and results, and chemical kinetic models. Decisions that deviate from this best practice must be discussed with the group leaders. The Coscine team also maintains a news website and a mailing list, which you can subscribe to for the latest updates.

4.1 Fundamentals about Coscine

Coscine uses a hierarchical (tree-like) model for all data. Every tree comprises two types of nodes: “Project” nodes and “resource” nodes. Project nodes are

used within a chosen tree to explain the structure of data. Resource nodes are leaves of the tree, i.e., they have no children and are used for storing data. Hence, a resource node corresponds to uploaded data, while (sub-)project nodes are used for documentation purposes. Note that entire folder structures can be uploaded into a resource. Different resource types are available. A list of all resource types available and their specification can be found on the corresponding help page of Coscine. Coscine manages permissions using three access models, referred to as owner, member, and guest. The owner of a project node has read and write access and can add new project and resource nodes. In addition, the owner can manage access permissions and project node settings. Guests have only read access and can view and download data. Note that access permissions are not inherited from the parent project node and can/need to be individually specified for each project node. A detailed description of managing access permission of projects can be found on the corresponding help page of Coscine

The hierarchical, tree-like structure of Coscine at ITV is illustrated in Figure 2. The baseline structure consists of a central ITV project node at the top of the hierarchy. A distinction between employees and test benches is introduced on the second level, providing sub-project nodes for each employee and test benches separately. While research data management is generally employee-based at ITV, this distinction is introduced to maintain consistency with the well-established server structures for experimental data. It is important to note that only experimental raw data are managed in the resource node of the test bench project nodes. Processed experimental data used, for example, in a publication, are managed within the corresponding employee project node.

The employee sub-project node will be created by the group leader during the first days at ITV, and the node will remain available in Coscine after the employee leaves the ITV. Each employee is responsible for managing the sub-project node and establishing a meaningful substructure for their data. Keep in mind that managing the nodes and moving project and resource nodes is not straightforward in Coscine and requires the creation of new nodes and re-uploading the data. Moreover, it follows from that limitation that the baseline structure is fixed and will not be updated, resulting in a constantly growing tree. **The accessibility of data is ensured by granting the corresponding group leader and director ownership rights for all project nodes.** This procedure is detailed in Section 4.2. Note that the tree structure shown for *Employee 1* and the *Jet Burner* test bench are examples. The examples in Section 4.3 illustrate how such substructures can be developed depending on the field.

4.2 Workflow

RDM with Coscine generally comprises the following steps:

1. Data generation, structuring, and documenting
2. Creation of a project node

Figure 2: Schematic representation of the Coscine structure for ITV.

3. Application for resources
4. Creation of resource node(s)
5. Data upload
6. Archiving

Data generation, structuring, and documenting: The workflow starts before the actual usage of Coscine during data generation by establishing a meaningful data structure and providing documentation. Note that data generation includes raw data generation (e.g., measured signals, simulation output, etc.) and processed data generation, and a distinction between both is highly recommended. A meaningful structure improves data usability and simplifies the subsequent upload process to Coscine. The examples in Section 4.3 illustrate how data can be structured and documented before uploading to Coscine. **All uploaded data must be complete and reproducible by the provided documentation.** Providing good README files can be a powerful tool to document data reproduction, particularly of processed data. README files can be used to document the overall project or subordinate data generation steps, such as creating a graph in a publication. A “good” README file is provided in an open file format and is processable by any text editor, e.g., MD (*preferred*)¹ or TXT. It is structured, including

1. a short description of the goal and main features to identify what problem the project solves,

¹The Markdown format provides rendering on GitLab and light formatting, e.g., headlines, tables, links, etc.

2. step-by-step instructions on setting up the environment (system requirements, installation, configuration, testing the environment),
3. basic usage commands and examples representing typical usage scenarios,
4. explanation of folder and file structure with a function description.

An exemplary README file is provided in the FlameMaster project or the C3MechV4.0 repository. Open file formats, such as CSV or YAML/JSON text files or HDF5, are preferred over proprietary formats. For example, DOCX and XLSX, are not open and should be converted to an open format before uploading to Coscine.

Creation of a project node: Once the data has been generated, structured, and documented, a project node must be created on Coscine if not yet available. Coscine will ask for some metadata. The recommended visibility is “Project Members” for ITV project nodes. As mentioned above, access rights are not inherited from the parent project node. To ensure that the corresponding group leader and director have access to the data, they have to be added as owners. Details about how to add users can be found on the corresponding help page of Coscine.

Application for resources: Storage requirements are known once the data has been generated, structured, and documented. Coscine features different resource types, which correspond to different storage options. A detailed description of the available resource types and a decision flow chart is provided on the corresponding help page of Coscine. An application is required for S3 resources and web storage of more than 100 GB (initially this is 25 GB, but the limit can be increased in the project settings). The links to the application forms can be found here. These links open up to a JARDS platform where proposals for storage space can be submitted (more information can be found in Appendix A). A Principal Investigator (PI) must be specified for each application. **Joachim Beckmann and Michael Gauding must always be the PI for experimental and simulation resources, respectively.**

Creation of resource nodes(s): After the project node creation and resource approval, resource nodes need to be created in Coscine according to the local structure of the data. Step-by-step instructions on creating resource nodes is provided on the corresponding help page of Coscine. The key steps are the resource type selection, Metadata profile selection, and resource metadata. The selection of the resource type follows the guidance provided on the corresponding help page of Coscine. Metadata profiles define a collection of metadata used to describe the data and will be separately presented in Section 4.2.1. In the final step, predefined metadata must be provided, such as the resource name or keywords. In addition, the visibility and license of the resource are asked about. **The recommended visibility is “Project Members” and the Creative Commons license CC BY 4.0 is recommended for published data.**

Data upload: How the data can be uploaded depends on the resource type. Often ITV’s resources are S3 resources, requiring clients to upload data. Different clients and their usage are described on the corresponding help page of Coscine. In addition, it is worth mentioning that Coscine features an Application Programming Interface for automating workflows.

Archiving Once the data reaches the end of its lifecycle, it should be archived. Technically, archiving means that the access permissions are set to read-only. In addition, archiving ensures that the data are stored for at least ten years in compliance with good scientific practices. An instruction on how to archive resources can be found on the corresponding help page of Coscine.

The following control mechanisms are implemented at ITV to ensure a seamless workflow from data generation to archiving, as outlined in this section. The control mechanisms are based on publications because of their exceptional importance in science. **After a publication is accepted (or the conference has taken place), a colleague reviews the uploaded data for completeness. All data required to reproduce figures in the paper must be included in an open file format.** A typical strategy is to select a random graph in the publication and try to reproduce it with the provided documentation (e.g., README files) and codes (either provided within the publication or accessible via GitLab). If this check is passed, the corresponding publication will be marked as complete in the employee’s status sheet. The status of each publication is reviewed at the biannual staff strategy meeting. To cover also non-published data, the group leader reviews project nodes for completeness before the employee leaves the ITV. This is part of the standard protocol and is noted in the checklist.

4.2.1 Metadata profiles

Metadata is additional data stored with the actual data to improve findability and usability. A Metadata profile defines a collection of metadata for a particular application and must be selected for every resource node added to a Coscine project node. **At ITV, it is expected that all uploaded data are complete and reproducible without the metadata provided by the Metadata profile.** Hence, the metadata provided by the Metadata profile is mainly intended at ITV to improve findability through Coscine’s search engine.

Metadata profiles specific to the requirements of data from ITV were developed. The Metadata profile ITVGeneral defines the baseline entries for all profiles and can be used if none of the application-specific profiles apply. Table 2 shows the required metadata and a description. In addition, Metadata profiles for different research fields at ITV exist:

- ITVCFD (Table 3) defines mandatory metadata for CFD (RANS, LES, DNS) simulation data.

- ITVSpeciation (Table 4) defines mandatory metadata for GC-MS and ToF-MS measurement data.
- ITVLBV (Table 5) defines mandatory metadata for Laminar Burning Velocity (LBV) measurement data.
- ITVEngine (Table 6) defines mandatory metadata for engine test bench measurements data.
- ITVKineticModel (Table 7) defines mandatory metadata for chemical kinetic models.
- ITVKineticModelValid (Table 8) defines mandatory metadata for databases used for chemical kinetic model validation.
- ITVLaserDiag (Table 9) defines mandatory metadata for laser diagnostic measurements data.

Table 2: Metadata profile: ITVGeneral.

Field Name	Description
Title	Provide a descriptive title for the data
Contact person	Provide the name (Firstname Surname, e.g., Max Mustermann) of the contact person.
Contact person ORCID	Provide the ORCID of the contact person.
Contact person email	Provide the email address of the contact person.
Producer / Author	Add all contributing persons. Use individual fields for each person (Plus-Button).
Keywords / Tags	Add relevant keywords. Use individual fields for each keyword (Plus-Button).
Legal information	Provide legal information (if applicable).
Date of creation	Provide the date of creation or provide the start and end dates for periods (Plus-button).
Funding	Add the funding project(s). Use acronyms from the internal project list, which is available on the ITV wiki. Use individual fields for each project (Plus-Button). If work is not funded, use ITV as the answer.
Status publication	Select one of the options: published, not published
Publication title	Provide the title of the publication.
Publication journal/conference	Provide the journal or conference name of the publication.
Publication DOI	Provide the DOI for the publication.
Comments / Explanation	Provide comments and explanations related to the data.

Table 3: Metadata profile: ITVCFD.

Field Name	Description
Software	Specify the software used. For example, CIAO, Converge, Fluent, etc. Use a separate field for each software (Plus-Button).
Git clone URL	If applicable, provide the Git clone URL of the code repository. Use a separate field for each repository (Plus-Button).
Version number / Git hash	Provide the version number or Git hash of the version used for the simulations. Use a separate field for each version number / Git hash (Plus-Button). Make sure that the same order as for the software and the Git clone URL list is used.
Simulation configuration	Describe briefly the configuration of the simulation. For example, premixed jet flame, non-premixed jet flame, piloted spray flame, etc. If the dataset contains several configurations, use a separate field for each configuration (Plus-Button).
Simulation type	Describe the simulation type. For example, 3D LES, 3D DNS, 2D laminar, etc. If the dataset contains several types, use a separate field for each type (Plus-Button).
Quantities of interest	Provide the main quantities of interest. For example, mean temperature, joint PDF of mixture fraction and progress variable, etc. Use a separate field for each quantity of interest (Plus-Button).
Solver specification	Provide solver specifications. For example, CIAO Low-Mach, CIAO compressible, etc. If several solvers were used, use a separate field for each solver (Plus-Button).
Combustion model	Provide information about the combustion model. For example, none reactive, finite-rate chemistry, tabulated premixed, tabulated non-premixed, etc. If several combustion models were used, use a separate field for each model (Plus-Button).
Multiphysics	Describe additional multiphysics that is relevant to the case. For example, Lagrangian Spray, Nanoparticle formation, Soot, etc. Use a separate field for each multiphysics process (Plus-Button).
HPC system	Specify the name of the HPC system used for the simulations. If several were used, specify them all. Use a separate field for each HPC system (Plus-Button).

Table 4: Metadata profile: ITVSpeciation.

Field Name	Description
Experimental setup	Provide a brief description of the experimental setup. For example, oxyflame counterflow burner, FSC counterflow burner, plate burner, etc. If several setups were used, use a separate field for each setup (Plus-Button).
Measurement technique	Provide the employed diagnostic technique. For example, GC-MS, ToF-MS, etc. Use a separate field for each technique (Plus-Button).
Fuels	Specify the fuel(s) used during the measurement. Use a separate field for each fuel (Plus-Button).
Conditions	Provide the main operating conditions. For example, the strain rate and oxidizer flow composition for a counterflow flame. Use a separate field for each quantity (Plus-Button).

Table 5: Metadata profile: ITVLBV.

Field Name	Description
Experimental setup	Provide a brief description of the experimental setup. For example, 0.9 l Spherical constant volume combustion chamber for optical and pressure-dependent measurement of laminar flame speed (DT1/DT2) without an intermediate ring. If several setups were used, use a separate field for each setup (Plus-Button).
Measurement technique	Provide the employed diagnostic technique, e.g., schlieren, shadowgraphy, natural luminosity, PIV, Rayleigh scattering, pressure method. Use a separate field for each method (Plus-Button).
Investigated substances	List what substances were investigated, e.g., CH ₄ , H ₂ , R ₃₂ . Use a separate field for each substance (Plus-Button).
Conditions	Explain what range of conditions (pressure, temperature, equivalence ratio) was investigated. For example, ambient conditions, phi=0.6, 0.7, 0.8, 0.9, 1.0, 1.1. Use a separate field for each quantity (Plus-Button).
Quantities of interest	List the quantities of interest. For example, "time series of pressures" in the case of raw data, and "time series of flame speeds" for processed data. Use a separate field for each quantity (Plus-Button).

Table 6: Metadata profile: ITVEngine.

Field Name	Description
TSN/RSN	Provide the unique number of the measurement. Test series number (TSNXXX) is used for measurement data, and reference series number (RSNXXX) is used for reference data. Use a separate field for each series (Plus-Button).
Experimental setup	Specify the injector and measurement equipment used.
Variation	Provide a brief description of the measurement variation, including its values. For example, lambda variation (LAM: 1.0, 1.4, 1.6), exhaust recirculation variation (EGR), pre-ignition investigation (PI). Use a separate field for each variation (Plus-Button).
Fuels	Specify the fuel(s) used during the measurement. Use a separate field for each fuel (Plus-Button).
Quantities of interest	Specify the main quantities of interest for the data. For example, the "pressure trace" in the case of raw data or the "combustion phasing" for processed data. Use a separate field for each quantity (Plus-Button).

Table 7: Metadata profile: ITVKineticModel.

Field Name	Description
Git clone URL kinetic model	Provide the Git clone URL for the kinetic model repository. For example, <code>git@git.rwth-aachen.de:ITV/mech.git</code>
Subdirectory	Provide the subdirectory in the git repository that contains the Chemkin files and species dictionary, e.g., <code>SootMechanisms/ITV_2015/Langer2021/kritika.liming/soot.langer</code>
Git hash kinetic model	Provide the git hash of the kinetic model.
Git clone URL validation database	Provide the Git clone URL for the validation database repository. For example, <code>git@git.rwth-aachen.de:ITV/mech.git</code> .
Git hash validation database	Provide the git hash of the commit used for the validation of the kinetic model.
Fuels	State their common name(s) and the name used in the model. Use a separate field for each fuel (Plus-Button).
Validation targets	Provide a summary of the validation targets considered. Use a separate field for each validation target (Plus-Button). Possible values are ignition delay time data from shock tubes (IDT(ST)), IDTs from rapid compression machines (IDT(RCM)), laminar burning velocities (LBV), extinction strain rates (ESR), species data from counterflow flames (CF), species data from jet-stirred reactors (JSR), or species data from flow reactors (FR).

Table 8: Metadata profile: ITVKineticModelValid.

Field Name	Description
Git clone URL validation database	Provide the Git clone URL for the validation data repository. The repository can be either a standalone repository for the kinetic model or a combined repository containing both the kinetic model and the validation data. An example of a combined repository is <code>git@git.rwth-aachen.de:ITV/mech.git</code>
Subdirectory	Provide the subdirectory in the git repository that contains the validation database, e.g., <code>GasolineSootUpdate/validation_cases/</code>
Git hash validation database	The git hash or tag of the version that is documented in Coscine. For example, this can be the git hash of the validation database as used for the release/publication of a kinetic model. Another status worth documenting would be a major change in the format of the data or the addition of new data.
Fuels	State their common name(s) and the name used in the model. Use a separate field for each fuel (Plus-Button).
Validation targets	Provide a summary of the validation targets considered. Use a separate field for each validation target (Plus-Button). Possible values are ignition delay time data from shock tubes (IDT(ST)), IDTs from rapid compression machines (IDT(RCM)), laminar burning velocities (LBV), extinction strain rates (ESR), species data from counterflow flames (CF), species data from jet-stirred reactors (JSR), or species data from flow reactors (FR).

Table 9: Metadata profile: ITVLaserDiag.

Field Name	Description
Experimental setup	Specify the used burner type. For example, counterflow burner, round jet burner, slot burner, industrial burner, etc. If several burners were used, use a separate field for each burner (Plus-Button).
Conditions	Provide the relevant conditions of the flame and the measurement location. For example, mixing length, equivalence ratio, oxidizer composition, fuel composition, Re/velocity range, pilot/co-flow conditions, height above nozzle, etc.
Measurement technique	Provide the measurement techniques used. For example, LIF, LIPF, LIBS, Raman Scattering, Rayleigh Scattering, LII, PIV, etc. Use a separate field for each technique (Plus-Button).
Acquisition settings	Provide the settings of the measurement system. For example, frequency, gate timing, online processing (binning, accumulation), background correction, etc.

4.3 Examples

This section presents six best-practice examples, one for each field. The examples are categorized as a data set or publication, demonstrating the separation of raw data generation from processed data. The data set examples demonstrate how to store and document simulation or experimental data, while the publication examples guide the preparation of a publication.

4.3.1 Example 1: Large Eddy Simulation of Nanoparticle Formation in the SpraySyn Flame (Data set)

The following example covers the Large Eddy Simulation (LES) data used for the publication of Fröde et al. [4]. Four simulations were performed, covering one simulation without precursor (undoped) and three with precursor (doped). Within the doped cases, three different precursor consumption models were tested assuming instantaneous inception (InstInc), finite rate inception (FiniteInc), and finite rate inception plus adsorption (FiniteIncAds). The data are structured in the following directories:

The data set splits up on the top level into the chemtable generation and the actual LES data. The chemtable generation covers three steps: the Burner-Stabilized Flame (BSF) computation to estimate the pilot flame, the generation of flamelet solutions, and the creation of the final chemtable. A directory exists for each of the steps. In addition, the kinetic models used are provided in the directory `flamelets`. A README file is provided in every directory, describing the usage, meaning, and important references (e.g., the reference to the kinetic model) of the files contained in it. For example, the directory `createChemtable` contains the following files:

```
createChemtable
├── convertTable.input
├── createChemtable.input
├── getNames.sh
└── README.txt
```

The directory `les` covers the grid generation (`grid`), required input files (`input`), and the simulation output (`runs`). The simulation results are organized according to the structure used in the paper [4]. Again, every directory contains a README file providing documentation. For example, the directory `InstInc` contains the following file:

```
InstInc
├── data.start
├── data.out
├── part.start
├── part.out
├── spraySyn_flame.input
├── links.sh
├── RunInfo.txt
└── README.txt
```

The data set is uploaded into one resource node using the application profile ITVCFD shown in Table 10. The resource node could be placed in the tree under *Data from ITV* → *Employees* → *Fabian Fröde* → *Simulation Data* → *SpraySyn Burner*

Table 10: Example application of ITVCFD within Example 1

Field Name	Response
Title	Large eddy simulation of nanoparticle formation in the SpraySyn flame: Impact of gas-phase chemistry
Contact person	Fabian Fröde
Contact person ORCID	0009-0009-2215-2762
Contact person email	f.froede@itv.rwth-aachen.de
Producer / Author	Fabian Fröde
Keywords / Tags	LES, nanoparticle formation, Method of Moments, FPVA, HMOM, precursor chemistry, adsorption, SpaySyn, spray flame synthesis
Legal information	none
Date creation	04-2023
Funding	SPP1980
Status publication	published
Publication title	Large eddy simulation of iron oxide formation in a laboratory spray flame
Publication journal/conference	Applications in Energy and Combustion Science
Publication DOI	10.1016/j.jaecs.2023.100191
Comments / Explanation	Relevance of precursor chemistry and adsorption on the nanoparticle formation in the SpraySyn flame.
Software	CIAO
Git clone URL	https://git.rwth-aachen.de/fabian.froede/SPP_1980
Version number / Git hash	fca834051cab10ea3fe2f46d2ec291df6520e3b5
Simulation configuration	Piloted spray flame
Simulation type	3D LES
Quantities of interest	Temperature, mixture fraction, droplet statistics, particle moments, particle diameters
Solver specification	CIAO Low-Mach
Combustion model	Three-stream flamelet progress variable approach (FPVA)
Multiphysics	Lagrangian spray, moment-based nanoparticle model
HPC system	CLAIX-2018

4.3.2 Example 2: The Role of C3 and C4 Species in Forming Naphthalene in Counterflow Diffusion Flames (Data set)

The following example covers the gas chromatograph (GC) speciation data used for the publication of Hellmuth et al. [8]. Two flames were probed multiple times, and numerous calibration measurements were performed. The data are structured in the following directories:

The directory contains three sub-directories: `01.Measurement_data` has a folder for each measurement, i.e., the analysis of one sample. A flame set comprises 16 measurements. A calibration set contains four or more measurements. Each measurement folder contains the recorded GC detector signals, e.g., `DATA.MS` for the mass-selective detector, and information on the method (`acqmeth.txt`) for generating the data. More on the acquisition methods of the

GC and the gas measurement system (GMS) is stored in `02_GC_methods` and `03_GMS_methods`, respectively. The data set could be placed in the tree under *Data from ITV → Test Benches → Gas chromatograph → Data* and directly linked to the publication.

Table 11: Example application of ITVSpeciation.

Field Name	Response
Title	The role of C ₃ and C ₄ species in forming naphthalene in counterflow diffusion flames
Contact person	Maximilian Hellmuth
Contact person ORCID	0000-0003-2325-9798
Contact person email	m.hellmuth@itv.rwth-aachen.de
Producer / Author	Maximilian Hellmuth
Keywords / Tags	Counterflow diffusion flame; Speciation measurement; Allene; 1-Buten-3-yne (C ₄ H ₄ , vinylacetylene); Naphthalene
Legal information	none
Date of creation	08-2023 - 11-2023
Funding	FSC
Status publication	published
Publication title	The role of C ₃ and C ₄ species in forming naphthalene in counterflow diffusion flames
Publication journal / conference	Proceedings of the Combustion Institute
Publication DOI	10.1016/j.proci.2024.105620
Comment / Explanation	Provide fresh insights into the role of C ₄ chemistry regarding aromatics formation by introducing 1-buten-3-yne (C ₄ H ₄) as fuel for the first time in counterflow diffusion flames.
Experimental setup	Oxyflame counterflow burner
Measurement technique	GC-MS and ToF-MS
Fuels	C3, C3+C4
Conditions	Strain rate of 60 s ⁻¹ (momentum balance); C3 flame: fuel flow: 5 % allene, oxidizer flow: 20 % oxygen, diluent: argon; C3+C4 flame: fuel flow: 3.5 % allene & 1.2 % 1-buten-3-yne/vinylacetylene, oxidizer flow: 19.9 % oxygen, diluent: argon.

4.3.3 Example 3: LII measurements of soot formation characteristics in ethylene and acetylene counterflow diffusion flames blended with dimethyl carbonate and methyl formate (Data set)

The following example covers the raw data from LII measurements in ethylene and acetylene-based counterflow diffusion flames blended with DMC and MeFo as used for the publication of Cameron et al. [1].

The data are uploaded in one resource node exemplary placed under *Data from ITV* → *Test Benches* → *Jet Burner*. The data are structured in the following directories:

```
LII
├── 01.Flame_properties
├── 02.Raw_data
│   ├── YYYYMMDD_<name of measurement>
│   │   ├── Settings.txt
│   │   ├── Data.spe
│   │   └── Data.mat
```

A README file containing information on the structure and contents of the directory is placed on the first level. Further documentation of the operating conditions is given in the directory `01.Flame_properties`. The directory `02.Raw_data` contains for every measurement day the recorded raw data. Besides the raw data files (`Data.spe` and `Data.mat`), each measurement directory contains a `txt` file with a detailed specification of the LII setup. The respective application profile response is given in Table 12.

Table 12: Example application of ITVLaserDiag

Field Name	Description
Title	LII measurements of soot formation in ethylene and acetylene counterflow diffusion flames blended with DMC and MeFo
Contact person	Florence Cameron
Contact person ORCID	
Contact person email	f.cameron@itv.rwth-aachen.de
Producer / Author	Yihua Ren
Keywords / Tags	In-situ laser diagnostics, Oxygenated fuels, Soot formation, synergistic effect
Legal information	none
Date of creation	06-2021 - 07-2021
Funding	FSC, NAMOSYN, HumboldtRen
Status publication	published
Publication title	In-situ laser diagnostic and numerical investigations of soot formation characteristics in ethylene and acetylene counterflow diffusion flames blended with dimethyl carbonate and methyl formate
Publication journal / conference	Proceedings of the Combustion Institute
Publication DOI	10.1016/j.proci.2022.07.219
Comment / Explanation	Effect of fuel blending on ethylene and acetylene soot formation
Experimental setup	Counterflow burner (FSC)
Conditions	Strain rate of 35 s ⁻¹ ; oxidizer: air, T = 298K; fuel: C ₂ H ₄ -based flames: $Y_{base,1,start} = 0.5$, $Y_{N2,1,start}=0.5$, $Y_{add}=0-0.36$, T=400K; C ₂ H ₂ -based flames: $Y_{base,1,start} = 0.15$, $Y_{N2,1,start}=0.85$, $Y_{add}=0-0.4$, T=400K; HAB = 2-18mm
Measurement technique	LII
Acquisition settings	J = 0.2 J/cm ² ; gate delay = 116 ns; gate width = 75 ns, acc = 50

4.3.4 Example 4: A Microgravity Flame Speed Study on Refrigerant Mixtures of 2,3,3,3-Tetrafluoropropene (R1234yf) and Difluoromethane (R32) (Publication)

The following example covers the conference paper by Hesse et al. [9]. Two refrigerants, R32 and R1234yf, and their blends were investigated in the spherical combustion chamber. Experiments were conducted in microgravity at the "Zentrum für angewandte Raumfahrttechnologie und Mikrogravitation" (ZARM). The flames were recorded for a large spectrum of temperature, pressure, and equivalence ratio by optical acquisition of the flame radius in a Schlieren system and by measurement of the pressure during the flame propagation.

The data are uploaded in one resource node exemplary placed under *Data from ITV → Employees → Raik Hesse → Publications → ECM 2023 R32/R1234yf Microgravity study* according to the structure depicted in Figure 2. The data are structured as follows:

```
2023.04_ECM_Rouen_R1234yf_R32
├── 00.Communication
├── 01.Supporting
├── 02.Abstract
├── 03.Paper
│   ├── LaTeX
│   └── Revisions
├── 04.Poster
├── 05.Literature
│   ├── cited_papers_pdfs
│   └── bib_file
├── 06.Data
│   ├── Experiment
│   │   ├── raw_data
│   │   ├── processed_optical_data
│   │   └── processed_pressure_data
│   └── Simulation
│       ├── Kinetic_Model
│       ├── FlameMaster_Input
│       └── FlameMaster_Output
├── 07.Software
│   ├── Image_processing
│   ├── Pressure_processing
│   └── Figure_creation
```

A comprehensive README file explains the structure of the research data in the top-level directory. If needed, README files are provided at other directory levels to describe the content and reproduction of the data and results. Important emails or other communication documents are stored in `00_Communication`. `01.Supporting` contains data that assists in completing the desired research

goal. In **02_Abstract**, the submitted abstract for the conference is stored. **03_Paper** contains the submitted paper, L^AT_EX source code, and internal revisions of the paper. **04_Poster** holds the presented poster on the topic. All cited papers of the study are stored in **05_Literature**. The processed data and the information about the underlying raw data are located in **06_Data**. The raw data information contains the persistent identifier of the corresponding Coscine resource node(s) and the corresponding resource node name within the "Test Benches" branch. Similarly, **07_Software** does not contain the source code but solely provides information on the corresponding code repositories on GitLab and information for the recreation of the results. The application profile response for this resource node using the application profile ITVLBV is provided in Table 13.

Table 13: Example application of ITVLBV.

Field Name	Description
Title	A Microgravity Flame Speed Study on Refrigerant Mixtures of 2,3,3,3-Tetrafluoropropene (R1234yf) and Difluoromethane (R32)
Contact person	Raik Hesse
Contact person ORCID	0000-0002-0957-5666
Contact person email	r.hesse@itv.rwth-aachen.de
Produces / Author	Roman Glaznev, Christian Schwenzer, Valeri Babushok, Greg T. Linteris, Heinz Pitsch, Joachim Beekmann
Keywords / Tags	Laminar flame speed, Refrigerant flammability, R32, R1234yf, Microgravity
Legal information	none
Date of creation	04/2023
Funding	DLR50WM2073, NIST70NANB21H157, ESA
Status publication	published
Publication title	A microgravity flame speed study on refrigerant mixtures of 2,3,3,3-Tetrafluoropropene (R1234yf) and difluoromethane (R32)
Publication journal / conference	European Combustion Meeting 2023
Publication DOI	
Comments / Explanation	Refrigerant blending ratio effect on laminar flame speed
Experimental setup	0.9 l Spherical constant volume combustion chamber for optical and pressure-dependent measurement of laminar flame speed
Measurement technique	Schlieren, pressure-rise
Investigated substances	2,3,3,3-Tetrafluoropropene (R1234yf) and difluoromethane (R32)
Conditions	$X_{R1234yf} = 0\%, 30\%, 50\%, 100\%$; $\phi = 1.1, 1.3$; $T_0 = 335$ K, $p_0 = 300$ kPa
Quantities of interest	Time series of flame speed over stretch, time series of flame speed over pressure

4.3.5 Example 5: Improved Kinetics and Methodology to Predict Methanol Oxidation and Nitrogen Oxides with RANS 3D-CFD for Spark-Ignition Engines (Publication)

The following example covers the paper in preparation by Golc et al. The target of the paper is the development of a methanol mechanism for RANS CFD simulations with a focus on NO_x prediction of methanol fuel. The experiments were conducted at the engine testbench of ITV, and the simulations have been performed on the RWTH Claix cluster with CONVERGE CFD. Three operations points with different λ - and EGR-ratios have been chosen to validate the mechanism.

The data are uploaded in one resource node, which can exemplarily placed under *Data from ITV* → *Employees* → *Domink Golc* → *Publications* → *Fuel MeOH Mechanism Engine* according to the structure depicted in Figure 2. The data are structured within the resource node as follows:

```
2025_01_FUEL_MeOH_Mechanism_Engine
├── 01_Abstract
├── 02_Paper
│   ├── LaTeX
│   └── Revisions
├── 03_Measurement_Data
│   ├── TSNXXX_MPXXX
│   │   └── IND
│   │       └── TSNXXX_MPXXX
├── 04_Simulation_Data
├── 05_MATLAB
├── 06_Literature
│   ├── cited_papers_pdfs
│   └── bib_file
└── 07_Software
```

At the top-level directory, a comprehensive README file is placed to explain the structure of the research data. **01_Abstract** contains the submitted abstract for the conference. **02_Paper** includes the submitted paper, the L^AT_EX source code, and internal revisions of the paper. **03_Measurement_Data** comprises the post-processed experimental data and the reference to the corresponding raw data. Again, the reference is provided using the persistent identifier of the corresponding resource nodes. For each operating point, an individual directory exists, including the cycle-averaged data and the single-cycle data, supplied in directory **IND**. **04_Simulation_Data** references the simulation data stored in an individual resource node using the application profile ITVCFD. **05_MATLAB** contains all plotting and additional post-processing scripts used for the study. **06_Literature** covers all cited PDFs and the used bib file for the paper. Finally, **07_Software** provides the GitLab repository information and version number for the main post-processing script that converts the raw data to the processed

data available in `03_Measurment_Data`.

The ITVEngine application profile response for this resource node is provided in Table 6.

Table 14: Example application of ITVEngine.

Field Name	Description
Title	Improved Kinetics and Methodology to Predict Methanol Oxidation and Nitrogen Oxides with RANS 3D-CFD for Spark-Ignition Engines.
Contact person	Dominik Golc
Contact person ORCID	
Contact person email	d.golc@itv.rwth-aachen.de
Producer / Author	Miguel Bueneflor, Francesca Loffredo, Joachim Beeckmann, Heinz Pitsch, Stefania Esposito
Keywords / Tags	Engine, Methanol, RANS-CFD, mechanism, e-fuels
Legal information	none
Date of creation	01/2025
Funding	Ford Alliance
Status publication	not published
Publication title	
Publication journal / conference	
Publication DOI	
Comments / Explanation	Validation of a new mechanism for NO _x prediction in CONVERGE CFD for a broad variation of parameters.
TSN/RSN	TSN132_MP017, TSN134_MP014, TSN141_MP012 and TSN141_MP015.
Experimental setup	The engine has been operated with the DI injector and three sensors for cylinder pressure indication
Variation	EGR: 20%, LAM: 1.0, 1.4, and 1.6
Fuels	Methanol
Quantities of interest	Pressure trace, exhaust gas emissions, heat release rate, in-cylinder temperature, indicated mean effective pressure, combustion phasing.

4.3.6 A detailed chemical kinetic model for aromatics formation (Data set)

Chemical kinetic models used in various ways to perform reacting flow simulations are among the most commonly shared data at ITV. Here, a detailed chemical kinetic model for aromatics formation is considered as an example to explain the application profile in Table 7. Langer et al. [13] developed this detailed model to analyze small hydrocarbon and gasoline surrogate fuel combustion, but the introduced application profile can also be applied to other kinetic models, including models for different fuels or reduced and optimized models. The de facto standard for providing chemical kinetic models is the CHEMKIN format [12, 10, 11]. Due to the wide availability of CHEMKIN format parsers, this format must always be used as the basis for kinetic model files, and additionally required data, such as data on covalent bonding, multiplicities, excitation states, or species lumping, must be provided in a backward compatible, machine-readable manner. For the detailed model of Langer et al. [13], the following files implement these requirements:

```
soot_langer/  
├── ITV_PAH.mech  
├── ITV_PAH.thermo  
├── ITV_PAH.trans  
├── species_list_default.json  
├── make_species_dict.py  
├── style_files_spec_dict  
│   ├── hyphenat.sty  
│   ├── placeins.sty  
│   ├── url.sty  
│   └── xurl.sty
```

The first three files are the CHEMKIN files, which provide gas-phase kinetics, thermochemistry, and transport data. The reader is referred to the literature for a discussion of this format [12, 10, 11]. Langer et al. [13] amended the thermochemistry files by machine-readable comments that provide additional information on the molecular structure of species through International Chemical Identifiers (InChIs) [7, 6] and Simplified Molecular Input Line Entry System (SMILES) formulas [20]. Recently, Pratali Maffei et al. [5] extended this approach to a rigorously defined species model by introducing species definitions based on species multiplicities and excitation states in addition to molecular structure data. This species model is adopted for more recent versions of the Langer et al. [13]. Like Pratali Maffei et al. [5], Langer et al. [13] implemented a Python script, which can be executed to check the numerous constraints on the species data [5] or to generate documentation. The following commands can be executed to perform all checks and generate a documentation:

```
$ pip3 install rdkit CairoSVG gitpython --user  
$ ./make_species_dict.py
```

```
$ cd SpeciesDict
$ pdflatex species_dict.tex
```

The metadata for the kinetic model of Langer et al. [13] are summarized in Table 15. The resource node is placed in the tree under *Data from ITV* → *Employees* → *Raymond Langer* → *Kinetic models*.

Similar to a complex source code, chemical kinetic models are expected to be developed using a Git repository. Therefore, the resource type of the node is “GitLab.” The “Repository kinetic model” field provides the repository location, which can be used with the git clone command, and the field “Git hash kinetic model” enables access to the exact model version that was documented in Coscine. Hence, continued use of the repository is possible and even encouraged, and the metadata in Coscine is considered the documentation of a snapshot of a relevant model version. There are several reasons for creating such a snapshot. The submission and acceptance of a peer-reviewed paper are typical, and Table 15 provides metadata documenting the model developed by Langer et al. [13] after acceptance of their manuscript. However, a new resource node can also be added when a researcher presents results obtained with a work-in-progress version of a model in a meeting or a seminar. A new resource node must be created when a model developer provides a model to a colleague. The application profile summarizes the validation range by specifying considered fuels and a list of validation targets. However, further validation details are provided in a separate resource node, an instance of the validation database “ITVKineticModelValid,” which is discussed in the following subsection. The validation database used to validate a kinetic model should be documented using the fields “Repository validation database” and “Git hash validation database.” A kinetic model and a validation database may be maintained in the same repository, as is the case for the ITV_PAH2023 kinetic model described in Table 15.

4.3.7 A validation database a detailed chemical kinetic model (Data set)

Validation databases support various tasks related to chemical kinetic modeling, such as developing detailed chemical kinetic models (as discussed in the previous subsection), comparing and benchmarking different kinetic models, and performing model reduction or optimization. Since the data used in these tasks are not specific to a single model, they must be managed independently.

Like kinetic models, the relevant data for validation databases, typically collected from the literature, must be managed in a git repository. The metadata fields relevant to validation databases are outlined in Table 8. As the fields overlap those in Table 7 for chemical kinetic models, the reader is referred to the previous subsection for a discussion. The example validation database discussed in this section is the one employed for the work of Langer et al. [13]. Table 16 shows the metadata for this database, which has the following directory structure:

```
validation_cases/
└─ ITV_Gasoline_Validation_Cases_Cai2015+2019/
```

```
|
|_ BurningVelocityClean/
|_ CounterflowFlames/
|_ FR/
|_ IgnitionDelay/
|_ JSR/
|_ README.md
|_ submit.sh
|_ submit_all.sh
```

The top-level README.md file provides detailed instructions on how to use the validation cases, which are organized by quantity of interest or, in the case of speciation data, configuration type. Within these directories, the cases are organized by fuel composition (not shown), where each subdirectory provides experimental data provided in text files (preferably YAML or CSV format) and scripts for plotting the data (preferably Python). Inlet, initial, and boundary conditions are stored as FlameMaster input files or text files (preferably YAML format) in conjunction with scripts that generate the FlameMaster input files (preferably Python). A script called “run.sh” must be added for each separate validation target that can be used to perform the FlameMaster simulations and generate the figures comparing the measured and predicted results. The top-level shell scripts can be executed to submit jobs that perform simulations of all validation cases on the HPC system.

Table 15: Example application of ITVKineticModel.

Field Name	Response
Title	A detailed kinetic model for aromatics formation from small hydrocarbon and gasoline surrogate fuel combustion
Contact person	Raymond Langer
Contact person ORCID	0000-0001-7309-4544
Contact person email	r.langer@itv.rwth-aachen.de
Producer / Author	Qian Mao, Heinz Pitsch
Keywords / Tags	PAH; chemical kinetic modeling; flux analysis
Legal information	none
Date creation	23-06-2022
Funding	The CRG project under project number URF/1/4688-01-01 funded by KAUST
Status publication	published
Publication title	A detailed kinetic model for aromatics formation from small hydrocarbon and gasoline surrogate fuel combustion
Publication journal / conference	Combustion and Flame
Publication DOI	doi.org/10.1016/j.combustflame.2022.112574
Comments / Explanation	The ITV model is constantly updated; ask members of the kinetics group for recommendations on which kinetic model should be used for a target application.
Git clone URL kinetic model	git@git.rwth-aachen.de:ITV/mech.git
Subdirectory	SootMechanisms/ITV_2015/Langer2021/kritika_liming/soot_langer
Git hash kinetic model	9351351f41a05561b4983cac1d2eba9746dc2564
Git clone URL validation database	git@git.rwth-aachen.de:ITV/mech.git
Git hash validation database	9351351f41a05561b4983cac1d2eba9746dc2564
Fuels	<i>n</i> -heptane (<i>n</i> -C ₇ H ₁₆), <i>iso</i> -octane (<i>i</i> -C ₈ H ₁₈), toluene (A ₁ CH ₃), ...
Validation targets	IDT(ST), IDT(RCM), LBV, CF, JSR, FR

Table 16: Example application of ITVKineticModelValid.

Field Name	Response
Title	ITV kinetic model validation database
Contact person	Raymond Langer
Contact person ORCID	0000-0001-7309-4544
Contact person email	r.langer@itv.rwth-aachen.de
Producer / Author	Qian Mao, Francesca Loffredo, Sanket Girhe, Heinz Pitsch
Keywords / Tags	chemical kinetic model validation; IDT; LBV; speciation; PAH
Legal information	none
Date creation	23-06-2022
Funding	This work received financial support from various projects.
Status publication	not published
Publication title	
Publication journal / conference	
Publication DOI	
Comments / Explanation	This is a central repository for collecting kinetic model validation data used at ITV.
Git clone URL	git@git.rwth-aachen.de:ITV/mech.git
validation database	
Subdirectory	GasolineSootUpdate/validation_cases
Git hash validation database	9351351f41a05561b4983cac1d2eba9746dc2564
Fuels	Methane (CH ₄), <i>n</i> -heptane (<i>n</i> -C ₇ H ₁₆), toluene (A ₁ CH ₃), ...
Validation targets	IDT(ST), IDT(RCM), LBV, CF, JSR, FR

A Applying for S3 storage via JARDS

Each project automatically gets 25 GB of storage, which can be increased up to 100 GB via the *Quota Settings* page. To apply for more than 100 GB of storage resources, it is required to submit an application. Among the different available resource types (available here), S3 resources are the preferred choice for the storage of large data. This resource type is only available after successfully applying for storage. The applications must be submitted via the JARDS platform (link). The process is similar to what is required for computing time applications in CLAIX or other HPC systems. A Principal Investigator (PI) is required for each application. **Joachim Beeckmann and Michael Gauding must always be the PI for experimental and simulation resources, respectively.** The application must include the following information:

- Abstract
- Grand IDs (e.g., DFG grant number, Computing time grants)
- Amount of requested storage
- Type of data stored, such as HDF5 (widely used format for large structured data, easy to handle and with easily-accessible data structure), binary data, or other formats
- Description of the data and size distribution (e.g., DNS data from a non-premixed turbulent jet)
- Metadata profile (**Always use the custom ITV profiles defined in this guide, e.g., ITVCFD**)
- How the data will be transferred from/to Coscine (e.g., MinIO for direct transfer from HLRS to Coscine, see this link for more info on S3 clients)
- Additional info on metadata, data structure and findability (e.g., Coscine structure for ITV, directory structure, READMEs for data usage, unit conversion)

S3 storage applications must be saved in Coscine under the project *Coscine S3 storage, JARDS*, as done for the HPC computing time proposals. An example of a 125 TB storage application for DNS data of a non-premixed turbulent temporal jet flame [17] can be found in Coscine under the same project (JARDS S3 Proposal link). A clear description of the data structure and the metadata profiles used is crucial for such applications.

Acknowledgments

This work is funded by the Deutsche Forschungsgemeinschaft (DFG, German Research Foundation) under Germany’s Excellence Strategy – Cluster of Excellence 2186 “The Fuel Science Center” – ID: 390919832. SPP 2419 HyCAM

Coordination Funds provided by the DFG under project number 523792626 are gratefully acknowledged.

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